

Between saying and doing for ensuring energy resources supply: The case of Italy in time of crisis

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Introduction

In recent years, the number of countries affected by deep geopolitical crises has grown, with global economic effects on energy. Italy is still very dependent on foreign energy imports. In this framework, it is crucial to investigate how much issues related to energy security have been considered by Italian governments to protect country's economic interests. The aim of this paper is to analyze to what extent energy security issues have been addressed in Italian energy policies and what actions have been implemented, using a content analysis approach. The results obtained reveal useful insights into changing policy priorities in supply's security.

Methods

This paper uses a conceptual content analysis approach to analyze official reports on energy security of supply published by Italian energy authorities in the period 2000-2020. It consists in a two-stage process (Upadhyay et al., 2021). In the first stage, we have conducted a word-count of the reports for selected words. In the second stage, we have verified both tools and actions implemented for addressing security of supply issues in Italy. It is a flexible method for analyzing text data that allows to provide knowledge concerning the phenomenon under study (Hsieh and Shannon, 2005).

Results

Results of the first stage of the content analysis show that security of supply issues have been treated with different intensities over the past twenty years. With reference to the second stage of the content analysis, our findings show that many incentive tools have been used in Italy for energy efficiency, for the development of RES, to reduce polluting emissions, and to improve energy infrastructures. With reference to some, results are heterogeneous in that some indicators considered in our analysis, regarding

security of supply issues, show the achievement of positive results, while other indicators show a negative trend.

References

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